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**QUALITY AND SAFETY CONTROL OF UNRECORDED FRUIT SPIRITS
FROM SERBIA**

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The established tradition of unrecorded, homemade fruit spirits consumption has been identified as a health risk source, especially in countries located at the Balkan Peninsula, Central and Eastern Europe. Hence, 100 unrecorded fruit spirit samples from Serbia, divided into 6 types - plum, apricot, pear, quince, apple and grape pomace were analyzed for the presence of volatiles - acetaldehyde, ethyl acetate, methanol and higher alcohols (*n*-propanol, *iso*-butanol, *n*-butanol, *iso*-amyl alcohol and *n*-amyl alcohol). The AMPHORA chemical testing limits guideline was used for the safety assessment of the volatiles. Acetaldehyde, which may contribute to the carcinogenicity of alcoholic beverages, exceeded the limit of 50 g/hl pa in plum (5.3%) and grape pomace (6.7%) samples. Ethyl acetate was below the AMPHORA limit (1000 g/hl pa) in all samples. Methanol, which has been described to be the most common cause for surrogate toxicity, was above the limit (1000 g/hl pa) in pear (30.8%), plum (23,7%) and apricot (15,8%) samples. Higher alcohols, which have been speculated as a cause for liver cirrhosis in Eastern Europe, were found to be above the limit (1000 g/hl pa) only in apricot samples (5.3%). The application of canonical discriminant analysis (CDA) showed that plum and apricot spirits are generally characterized by higher levels of methanol in comparison to the other examined samples, while acetaldehyde dominates in grape pomace spirits. Distribution of higher alcohols among analyzed spirits was described by the following pattern: *n*-propanol – plum, *iso*-butanol and *n*-butanol – apricot, *iso*-amyl alcohol – quince and grape pomace. The obtained results suggest that control measures should be included in order to maintain the quality of homemade spirits and minimize the potential adverse health effects.

Keywords: Unrecorded fruit spirits, volatiles, quality and safety control, HSS-GC-FID